

PREPARATION, DIAGNOSIS AND EVALUATION OF THE BIOLOGICAL EFFICACY OF NEW DERIVATIVES OF THE OXAZEPINE RING

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Abstract: In the research, new derivatives of the oxazepine heptacyclic ring were prepared by the reaction of equal moles of the prepared codebases with phthalic anhydride, nuclear magnetic resonance spectroscopy, infrared spectroscopy and physical measurements were used to confirm the compounds formed, in addition, the melting degrees of the prepared compounds were determined. It was also examined how several prepared compounds affect the growth of two types of bacterial isolates *Klebsiella*, gram-negative and Gram-positive *Staphylococcus aureus*.

Keywords: Oxazepine, Biological activity.

1. Introduction

Oxazepine They are compounds with a heterogeneous and unsaturated seven-ring most often called oxazepine and may be saturated and called oxazepan(1) containing five carbon atoms and two heterogeneous atoms, an oxygen atom and a nitrogen atom(2) oxazepine compounds are non-aromatizing compounds and oxazepine compounds are of wide importance due to its biological activity in life, as in antihistamines (3), anticancer drugs (4), antivirals (5) painkillers (6), antifungals (7), antihistamines anticonvulsants (8), anticoagulants (9), antidepressants (10), non-narcotic antimicrobials (11), sedatives, and hypnotics (12).

2. Materials and Methode:

2.1. Material: All of the chemicals used in this study were obtained from BDH, Fluka, and Aldrich, without any further purification.

2.2. Equipment utilized: Melting points were measured with a thermoelectric melter 9300. KBr disk at 400–4000 cm⁻¹ scale, Shimadzu FT-IR 8400S spectrophotometer; Bruker equipment running at 400 MHz for ¹H-NMR and ¹³C-NMR spectra. Fluka silica gel plates with a thickness of 0.2 mm were used in thin-layer chromatography (TLC). UV light was used to achieve visibility after fluorescent silica gel G was used to activate the plates.

2.3. Preparation of Oxazepane [13]

The preparation was carried out by adding (0.01 mole) of the prepared five SHF bases with (0.01 mole) of the phthalic anhydride compound, after dissolving each of them in (15 ml) of dry benzene, mixing them in a conical flask, and the mixture was ascended for(12) hours, at a temperature of C 50, after which the reaction was cooled and obtained sediments of different colors and different percentages, purification and melting points were measured, as shown in Table (1).

Table (1) Some physical properties, percentage, reaction time, and Rf of oxazpine derivatives

Comp.No	X	Molecular Formula	M.P (C°)	Yield%	Color
Ar40	Cl-	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ N ₃ O ₃ Cl	178-180	80	Yellow
Ar42	NO ₂	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₅	190-192	82	Brown
Ar50	-Br	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ N ₃ O ₃ Br	176-178	78	White
Ar51	-N(CH ₃) ₂	C ₂₄ H ₂₂ N ₄ O ₃	175-177	76	White
Ar52	CH ₃ -	C ₂₃ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₃	184-186	82	Yellow

2.4. Evaluation of the biological activity

The effectiveness of the prepared compounds against bacteria was tested using the agar diffusion method[14-17]. After inoculating the culture medium with bacterial isolates, make holes in the Petri dishes using the cylinder-measuring method (according to USP 35). Using the driller: (40 microliters) of the prepared compounds in three concentrations are placed in each well and the plate is incubated at a temperature of (37 degrees Celsius) for (24) hours, then (24) hours and (48) hours later the results are read[18-22]. To demonstrate the sensitivity of the derivative used, which depends on the inhibitory diameter appearing in the Petri dish surrounding the well, where an increase in the inhibitory diameter means an increase[23-28]. The biological activity of the prepared compounds was compared with the inhibition diameter of standard antibiotics, using solutions such as amoxicillin and ciprofloxacin as control samples depending on the solutions used in the laboratory. Ministry of Health and based on World Health Organization tests[29-33].

3. Results and Discussion:

Several compounds had to be prepared for this investigation, as the scheme(1) shows.

Scheme (1): Path of the Ready Compounds

3.1. Characterization of Oxazepane derivatives[34]:

The infrared(IR) spectrum of the compound[Ar42] showed absorption beams within the range(1703 cm⁻¹) belonging to the actin of the carbonyl group lactone(O-CO), the appearance of an absorption beam at the range (1686 cm⁻¹), belonging to the actin of the carbonyl group lactam(lactam) (N-CO), absorption beams at the range(1517-1597 cm⁻¹), belonging to the actin(C=C) aromatization, the appearance of a bundle at(2925 cm⁻¹) belonging to the(CH₃) group and an absorption bundle was also observed at(3106 cm⁻¹), belonging to the (AR-h) aromatization range.

Table (2) shows the results of the infrared absorption (cm⁻¹) of oxazpine derivatives.

IR(KBr) cm ⁻¹						
Comp. No	X	C=O Lacton	ν (Ar-H)	C=C C	C=O Lacta, NBm	CH ₃
Ar40	Cl-	1764	3066	1597	1681	2911
Ar42	NO ₂	1703	3106	1517	1686	2925
Ar50	-Br	1708	3086	1600	1691	2934
Ar51	- N(CH ₃) ₂	1731	3006	1598	1698	2923
Ar52	CH ₃ -	1719	3074	1605	1688	2901

Figure (1) infrared spectrum of the compound (Ar42)

The NMR spectrum of the proton (¹H-NMR) of the compound [Ar42] showed signals at (ppm 8.37 – 6.87) belonging to the protons of the aromatic ring, while the signal visible at (ppm 6.35) belongs to the Proton of the (N-CH-O) group in the heptagonal ring, and the signal visible at (ppm 3.36) belongs to the protons of the (CH₃) group.

Figure (2): Proton NMR spectrum of the compound [Ar42]

The NMR spectrum of the carbon (^{13}C -NMR) of the compound [Ar42] showed a signal at (ppm174.23) belonging to the carbon atom of the carbonyl group ($\text{O}-\text{C}=\text{O}$) in the heptagonal ring, while the signal seen at (ppm163.34) belonging to the carbon atom of the carbonyl group ($\text{N}-\text{C}=\text{O}$) in the heptagonal ring, and the signals seen at (ppm151.02 - 112.50) belonging to the carbon is in the aromatic ring, while the signal visible at PPM 110.95 is due to the carbon atom of the $\text{N}-\text{Ch}-\text{o}$ group in the heptagonal ring. While the signal visible at PPM 29.32) is due to the carbon atom of the CH_3 group.

Figure (3): carbon NMR spectrum of the compound [Ar42]

3.4. Evaluation of Biological activity

These germs were chosen for their medical importance, as they cause many diseases, as well as where these germs differ in their resistance to antibiotics. The bioeffectiveness of some compounds prepared using the etching method was evaluated [35-40], and the level of inhibition (inhibition zone) was measured, where it was found that the prepared compounds have the ability to inhibit the growth of bacteria used with positive and negative types of gram dye in different proportions, and four compounds were used in the study of bacterial effectiveness (Ar52, Ar51, Ar50, Ar42, Ar40), so was the direct relationship between concentration and inhibition [41-44], as shown by Table (3).

Table (3): Antibiotics and other generated chemicals can prevent the growth

	Conc. m/m	Staphylococcus aureus+	Klebsiella-
Ar40	0.01	18	23
	0.001	6	17
	0.0001	2	15
Ar42	0.01	24	22
	0.001	10	18
	0.0001	6	16
Ar50	0.01	22	20
	0.001	16	16
	0.0001	10	10
Ar51	0.01	22	22
	0.001	14	16
	0.0001	10	12
Ar52	0.01	23	22
	0.001	16	14
	0.0001	11	10

Figure(4): shows the bioeffectiveness of some compounds prepared on the bacterium Klebsiella pneumonia

Figure (5): shows the bioeffectiveness of some compounds prepared on *Staphylococcus aureus* bacteria

Conclusion:

Using nuclear magnetic resonance spectroscopy, infrared spectroscopy, and spectrophotometry, the generated compounds were validated. In addition, its effectiveness against two different types of Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria has been proven, and it was found to be equivalent to that of the antibiotic amoxicillin.

References

1. Sulyman, Z. H., & Ahmed, N. G. (2020). Synthesis of New Oxazepine and Thiazolidine Compounds derived from Pyrimidine-2 (1H)-one. *Journal of Education and Science*, 29(2), 186-200.
2. Assadzadeh, F., Eshghi, H., & Afrough, T. (2023). An Efficient One-Pot and Regioselective Synthesis of Novel Heterocyclic Systems of 5, 6-Dihydrobenzo [b] Pyrimido [5, 4-f][1, 4] Oxazepine. *Polycyclic Aromatic Compounds*, 43(2), 1557-1565.
3. JB, P. (1981). Hofmann CM. Eudy NH. Day IP. Greenblatt EN. Safir SR. *J. Med. Chem*, 24, 154.
4. Ali, Z. H., Jber, N. R., & Abbas, A. K. (2023, February). Synthesis and characterization of new 1, 3-oxazepine compounds from P-Phenylenediamine as insecticide (Aphidoidea). In *AIP Conference Proceedings* (Vol. 2457, No. 1). AIP Publishing.
5. Campiani, G., Nacci, V., Fiorini, I., De Filippis, M. P., Garofalo, A., Greco, G., ... & Di Renzo, L. (1996). Pyrrolobenzothiazepinones and pyrrolobenzoxazepinones: novel and specific non-nucleoside HIV-1 reverse transcriptase inhibitors with antiviral activity. *Journal of Medicinal Chemistry*, 39(14), 2672-2680.
6. Saingar, S., Kumar, R., & Joshi, Y. C. (2011). Synthesis and biological activity of novel 1 H-1, 4-diazepines containing benzene sulfonyl piperazine moiety. *Medicinal Chemistry Research*, 20, 975-980.
7. Serrano-Wu, M. H., Laurent, D. R. S., Chen, Y., Huang, S., Lam, K. R., Matson, J. A., ... & Balasubramanian, B. N. (2002). Sordarin oxazepine derivatives as potent antifungal agents. *Bioorganic & medicinal chemistry letters*, 12(19), 2757-2760.
8. Ali, Z. H., Jber, N. R., & Abbas, A. K. (2023, February). Synthesis and characterization of new 1, 3-oxazepine compounds from P-Phenylenediamine as insecticide (Aphidoidea). In *AIP Conference Proceedings* (Vol. 2457, No. 1). AIP Publishing.

9. Mishra, J. K., Samanta, K., Jain, M., Dikshit, M., & Panda, G. (2010). Amino acid based enantiomerically pure 3-substituted benzofused heterocycles: A new class of antithrombotic agents. *Bioorganic & medicinal chemistry letters*, 20(1), 244-247.
10. Sleevi, M. C., Cale Jr, A. D., Gero, T. W., Jaques, L. W., Welstead, W. J., Johnson, A. F., ... & Jenkins, H. (1991). Optical isomers of rocastine and close analogs: synthesis and H1 antihistaminic activity of its enantiomers and their structural relationship to the classical antihistamines. *Journal of medicinal chemistry*, 34(4), 1314-1328.
11. Boureau, F., Laquais, B., Vadrot, M., & Willer, J. C. (1980). Human neuropharmacological findings with oxapadol (MD 720111), a new non-narcotic analgesic. *Experientia*, 36, 97-98.
12. Abbas, A. K., & Jber, N. R. (2020). Synthesis and estimation of biological activity of new oxazepine derivatives. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*, 12(2), 3750-3758.
13. Abdul-Wahid, J. H., Hameed, A. S., & Mohammed, A. K. (2016). Synthesis Characterization of Some New Heterocyclic Compounds Containing 1, 3-Oxazepine Ring. *Kirkuk Journal of Science*, 11(3), 237-247.
14. Dalaf, A. H., Saleh, M. J., & Saleh, J. N. (2024). GREEN SYNTHESIS, CHARACTERIZATION, AND MULTIFACETED EVALUATION OF THIAZOLIDINONE DERIVATIVES: A STUDY ON BIOLOGICAL AND LASER EFFICACY. *EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF MODERN MEDICINE AND PRACTICE*, 4(7), 155-168.
15. Talluh, A. W. A. S., Saleh, M. J., & Saleh, J. N. (2024). Preparation, Characterisation and Study of the Molecular Docking of Some Derivatives of the Tetrazole Ring and Evaluation of their Biological Activity. *World of Medicine: Journal of Biomedical Sciences*, 1(7), 15-23.
16. Saleh, M. J., Saleh, J. N., & Al-Badrany, K. (2024). PREPARATION, CHARACTERIZATION, AND EVALUATION OF THE BIOLOGICAL ACTIVITY OF PYRAZOLINE DERIVATIVES PREPARED USING A SOLID BASE CATALYST. *EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF MODERN MEDICINE AND PRACTICE*, 4(7), 25-32.
17. Talluh, A. W. A. S., Saleh, J. N., & Saleh, M. J. (2024). Preparation, Characterization and Evaluation of Biological Activity and Study of Molecular Docking of Some New Thiazoli-dine Derivatives.
18. Talluh, A. W. A. S., Saleh, M. J., Saleh, J. N., Al-Badrany, K., & mohammed saleh Al-Jubori, H. (2024). Preparation, characterization, and evaluation of the biological activity of new 2, 3-dihydroquinazoline-4-one derivatives. *EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF MODERN MEDICINE AND PRACTICE*, 4(4), 326-332.
19. Talluh, A. W. A. S. (2024). Preparation, Characterization, Evaluation of Biological Activity, and Study of Molecular Docking of Azetidine Derivatives. *Central Asian Journal of Medical and Natural Science*, 5(1), 608-616.
20. Aftan, M. M., Salih, H. K., & Talloh, A. A. (2021). Synthesis of new mesogenic Schiff bases ether with polar halogen Substituent and study their liquid crystalline properties. *Journal of Education and Scientific Studies*, 5(17).
21. Saleh, J. N., & Khalid, A. (2023). Synthesis, characterization and biological activity evaluation of some new pyrimidine derivatives by solid base catalyst AL₂O₃-OBa. *Central Asian Journal of Medical and Natural Science*, 4(4), 231-239.

22. Saleh, M. J., & Al-Badrany, K. A. (2023). Preparation, characterization of new 2-oxo pyran derivatives by AL₂O₃-OK solid base catalyst and biological activity evaluation. *Central Asian Journal of Medical and Natural Science*, 4(4), 222-230.
23. Al-Joboury, W. M., Al-Badrany, K. A., & Asli, N. J. (2022, November). N-alkylation of substituted 2-amino benzothiazoles by 1, 4-bis (bromo methyl) benzene on mixed oxides at room temperature and study their biological activity. In *AIP Conference Proceedings* (Vol. 2394, No. 1). AIP Publishing.
24. Al Rashidy, A. A. M., Al Badrany, K. A., & Al Garagoly, G. M. (2020, August). Spectrophotometric determination of sulphamethoxazole drug by new pyrazoline derived from 2, 4-dinitro phenyl hydrazine. In *Materials Science Forum* (Vol. 1002, pp. 350-359). Trans Tech Publications Ltd.
25. Mohamed, S. A., Hussein, M. S., & Al-badrany, K. A. (2022). Synthesis and characterization of pyrazolines and oxazapine derivatives using chalcones as precursor and evaluation of their biological activity. *Samarra Journal of Pure and Applied Science*, 4(4).
26. Al-Hadidi, O. A. F., Al-Badrany, K. A., & Al-Bajari, S. A. (2022). Synthesis some of thiazepine compounds from 2-carboxyaldehyde-5-methyl thiophene and study their biological activity on infected male rats epileptic. *Journal of Education and Scientific Studies*, 2(20).
27. Al-Badrany, K. A., Mohammed, A. S., & Alasadi, Y. K. (2019). Synthesis of some new 1, 3, 4-oxadiazole compounds derived from 1H-imidazole and study their biological activity. *Eurasian Journal of Biosciences*, 13(1), 501-507.
28. Al-Badrany, A. S. S., & Al, R. J. S. A. D. (2023). The Impact of the Digital Economy on International Trade, the Case of Egypt for the Period (1990-2020). *Integrated Journal for Research in Arts and Humanities*, 3(2), 163-173.
29. Al-Tufah, M. M., Jasim, S. S., & Al-Badrany, K. A. (2020). Synthesis and Antibacterial Evaluation of some New Pyrazole Derivatives. *Prof.(Dr) RK Sharma*, 20(3), 178.
30. Al-Badrany, K. A. (2024). THE USE OF 2-AMINOPYRAZINE AS A BASIC NUCLEOPHILE FOR THE PREPARATION OF NEW DERIVATIVES OF THE 5, 6-DIHYDROPYRIDINE-2 (1H-YLIDENE) CYANAMIDE RING, THEIR DIAGNOSIS, AND EVALUATION OF THEIR BACTERIAL EFFICACY. *EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF MODERN MEDICINE AND PRACTICE*, 4(5), 508-518.
31. Khairallah, B. A., Muhammad, F. M., Saleh, J. N., & Saleh, M. J. (2024). Preparation, Characterization, Biological Activity Evaluation, and Liquid Crystallography Study of New Diazepine Derivatives. *World of Medicine: Journal of Biomedical Sciences*, 1(7), 65-76.
32. Sattar Talluh, A. W. A., Saleh, J. N., Saleh, M. J., & Saleh Al-Jubori, H. M. (2024). Preparation and Characterization of New Imidazole Derivatives Derived From Hydrazones and Study of their Biological and Laser Efficacy. *Central Asian Journal of Theoretical and Applied Science*, 5(4), 202-211.
33. Muhammad, F. M., Khairallah, B. A., Saleh, M. J., & Saleh, J. N. (2024). Preparation and Characterization of New Rings of Oxazine Derivatives and Studying Their Biological and Laser Effectiveness and Molecular Docking. *Central Asian Journal of Theoretical and Applied Science*, 5(4), 190-201.
34. Abdul Wahed, A. S. T. (2024). Preparation and Evaluation of Bacterial Activity and Study of the Crystalline Properties of Some 1, 3-Oxazepine-4, 7-Dione Derivatives. *Central Asian Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sciences*, 5(2), 15-26.

35. Mohammed Jwher Saleh, Jamil Nadhem Saleh, Khalid Al-Badrany, Adil Hussein Dalaf, Reem Suhail Najm, & Abdul Wahed Abdul Sattar Talluh. (2024). Preparation And Evaluation Of The Biological Activity Of A 2- Amino Pyran Ring Using A Solid Base Catalyst. *Central Asian Journal of Medical and Natural Science*, 5(4), 130 - 138.
36. Mahmoud Mehdi Saleh, Jamil Nadhem Saleh, Fahad Farhan Rokan, & Mohammed Jwher Saleh. (2024). Synthesis, Characterization and evaluation of bacterial efficacy and study of molecular substrates of cobalt (II) complex[Co (2-(benzo[d]thiazol-2-yl)oxy) acetohydrazide) (H₂O) (Cl₂)]. *Central Asian Journal of Medical and Natural Science*, 5(4), 198 -.
37. Talluh, A. W. A. S., Saleh, M. J., Saleh, J. N., & Al-Jubori, H. M. S. (2024). Synthesis and Characterization of Some New Imine Graphene Derivatives and Evaluation of Their Biological Activity. *Central Asian Journal of Medical and Natural Science*, 5(4), 272-290.
38. Hamad, A. S., Shnak, Q. A., & Ali, M. H. (2023). Synthesis and Study of the Biological Activity of Some Oxazepine Containing the Pyrrolidine Ring. *Central Asian Journal of Medical and Natural Science*, 4(6), 806-816.
39. Najm, R. S., Shannak, Q. A., & Dalaf, A. H. (2023). Synthesis and Decoration of Aromatic Derivatives Nano Platelets by the Electric Method. *Azerbaijan Pharmaceutical and Pharmacotherapy Journal*, 22(2), 92-97.
40. Shannak, Q. A., Najim, T. M., & Madab, D. I. (2022). Evaluation of the level of vitamin D₃ in the blood serum of patients infected with COVID-19 in Al-Amiriya city. *Technium BioChemMed*, 3(2), 127-135.
41. Shannak, Q. A., Madab, D. I., & Mohammed, S. (2021). "PhD. Organic Chemistry, Ministry of Education, Salah Al-Din. *Annals of RSCB*, 25(6), 5432-5441.
42. Shannak, M. Q. A., Othman, I. A. W., Rasheed, M. K., & Mahmood, S. K. (2018). Synthesis and Characterization of New Some Binuclear Complexes for Some Transition Element Metals with Schiff Base ligand Derived from 1-Chloro-2-(2-Chloroethoxy) Ethane. *Eurasian Journal of Analytical Chemistry*, 13, 339-346.
43. Shannak, Q. A., Madab, D. I., Mohammed, S., & Alhiti, M. A. (2021). Effects of Ascorbic Acid Supplement and Furdivita extraction on Hematological Parameters, liver function tests and histopathological changes in Rabbits liver. *Annals of the Romanian Society for Cell Biology*, 25(6), 5432-5441.
44. Fadel, E. J., Shannak, Q. A., Alhiti, M. A., & Ali, S. M. (2021). Serum Protein Electrophoresis Plays a Role in the Diagnosis of Multiple Myeloma in Baghdad City Patients. *Annals of the Romanian Society for Cell Biology*, 6060-6065.